

Quantifying intermolecular interaction of one trinuclear Zn^{II} and one mononuclear Cd^{II} complex of pyrimidine based hexadentate Schiff base : Insights from Hirshfeld surface analysis

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Abstract : The Hirshfeld surface area was evaluated for both the complexes [Zn₃(L)₂Cl₆] (1) and [Cd(L)(H₂O)₂](ClO₄)₂ (2) [L = N₆ donor hexadentate Schiff base 2,4-bis[2-(pyridine-2-ylmethylidene)hydrazinyl]pyrimidine]. The Hirshfeld surface analysis quantify the rare Cl...Cl weak interaction in 1 and other molecular interactions e.g. C...H, H...H, C...C, π ... π present in the solid state of both complexes 1 and 2.

Keywords : Hirshfeld surface analysis, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complex, Cl-Cl interaction, weak interactions.

Introduction

Crystal engineering is a fascinating domain of research and deals with simple to complex problems related to intermolecular interactions in crystals. By their intuition and intelligence crystal engineers try to synthesize some predesigned molecular crystals having desirable properties with the knowledge of several molecular interactions which provide some stabilizing factor. Beside strong interactions various weak dispersive interactions, such as C-H... π , O-H...O, H...H¹⁻⁴ represents the skeleton of self assembly process and supramolecular building blocks.

Detailed comparison between molecular crystal structures, even structures containing the same molecule, is seldom straightforward and the rapid growth in the number of published structures has given impetus to the need to compare rapidly and contrast molecular crystal structures and, in so doing, to quantify the similarities and differences. Comparisons of this kind can be performed at

a number of levels, but where the aim is to understand the packing of crystal, especially for the purposes of crystal design and crystal engineering, an essential prerequisite is a whole-of-molecule approach, stripped of the biases inherent in focusing on a limited number of short atom-atom contacts that are assumed to be important. The Hirshfeld surface is becoming a valuable tool for analyzing intermolecular interactions while maintaining a whole-of-molecule approach. It is defined by the 0.5 isosurface of the weight function $W(r)$ [eq. (1)], the sum of spherical atom electron densities from the molecule of interest (the promolecule) divided by the same sum for the crystal (the procrystal). Inside the Hirshfeld surface the electron density of the promolecule dominates the procrystal. For points on the surface, distances to the nearest atoms outside, d_e , and inside, d_i , are readily defined, and we have used these properties, together with the identity of those atoms, to explore the type (C-H... π , O-H...O, H...H etc.) as well

as the proximity of intermolecular contacts in a molecular crystal. Here, we describe extensions to the suite of Hirshfeld surface tools with the goal of enabling quantitative comparison between intermolecular interactions in molecular crystals.

$$W(r) = \rho_{\text{Promolecule}}(r)/\rho_{\text{Procrystal}}(r) \\ = \sum_{A_{\text{molecule}}} \rho_A(r) / \sum_{A_{\text{crystal}}} \rho_A(r) \quad (1)$$

The distances d_e and d_i mapped on the Hirshfeld surface provide a three-dimensional picture of intermolecular close contacts in a crystal. They are also used to generate a fingerprint plot, a concise two-dimensional summary of intermolecular interactions in the crystal. However, when mapped on the surface d_e and d_i have the limitation that they do not take into account the relative size of atoms, so close contacts between large atoms are often not effectively highlighted. To overcome this we define a normalized contact distance, d_{norm} [eq. (2)], where r^{vdW} is the van der Waals (vdW) radius of the appropriate atom internal or external to the surface. d_{norm} is negative where contacts shorter than vdW separations occur, and positive for contacts greater than vdW separations, and is displayed using a red-white-blue colour scheme, where red highlights shorter contacts, white is used for contacts around the vdW separation, and blue is for longer contacts. Our focus is of course on the shorter contacts, which become brighter and larger red spots as internuclear separations decrease. Moreover, because d_{norm} is symmetric in d_e and d_i , any close intermolecular contact will be characterized by two identical red regions, although not necessarily on the same molecule.

$$d_{\text{norm}} = [(d_i - r_i^{\text{vdW}})/r_i^{\text{vdW}}] \\ + [(d_e - r_e^{\text{vdW}})/r_e^{\text{vdW}}] \quad (2)$$

There are a lot of molecular interactions that are responsible to play a pivotal role in crystal packing in solid state which induces the supramolecular interactions in solid phase. These types of interactions which are quantified by Hirshfeld surface analysis are relatively common for small and conjugated organic molecules but there are a few examples where molecular interactions are decoded from Hirshfeld surface analysis for a metal chelated complex.

The weak intermolecular interactions between chlorine atoms have been a subject of recent interest and debate for many decades⁵. Two hypotheses have been put

forward to account for the observed Cl...Cl interaction. One explanation is that there is a specific attractive force which produces short contacts in certain directions and this intermolecular interaction is variously referred to as a "donor-acceptor", "secondary", or "charge-transfer" interaction, or "incipient electrophilic and nucleophilic attack", involving a weak form of covalent bonding. The alternative hypothesis is that the atomic charge density has a non spherical shape, producing a decreased repulsion and thus closer Cl...Cl contacts in certain direction^{6,7}. This type of interaction is resolved using various analyses of experimental crystal structure data and theoretical calculations by different authors⁸. As molecular size and complexity increase, it becomes a daunting task to decipher the numerous intermolecular interactions in a molecular crystal⁹. A novel approach to the problem was recently introduced by Spackman and co-workers based on the Hirshfeld surface of a molecule in a crystal¹⁰.

Here we have carried out the Hirshfeld surface analysis to quantify the rare Cl...Cl weak interaction in **1** and other molecular interactions e.g. C...H, H...H, C...C present in the solid state of both complexes **1** and **2**. A brief discussion on the existence and nature of short Cl...Cl non-bonded contacts (3.2 to 3.6 Å) in molecular crystals was reported by Mirsky *et al.*¹¹ but this type of interaction is rare in metal complexes¹². It is to be noted that the Cl(1)...Cl(3) interactive distance (3.222 Å) is probably the "shortest" Cl...Cl distance observed in metal complexes till date which is one of the factors for stabilization of the crystal packing.

Computational method :

McKinnon *et al.*² have recently presented a detailed review of the application of the Hirshfeld surface¹³ to explain and describe a wide variety of molecular crystal structures, and it was clear from the work that graphical tools based on the Hirshfeld surface and the associated two dimensional (2D) fingerprint plot¹⁴ offered considerable promise for exploring packing modes and intermolecular interactions in molecular crystals. In this paper, according to Hirshfeld surface-based tools, we use Crystal Explorer¹⁵ for decoding of intermolecular interactions in crystal network. The 3D shape and breakdown of fingerprint plots¹⁶ (existing new techniques and tools based on the Hirshfeld surface and already incorporated in Crystal Explorer computer program) were applied to visualize and explore intermolecular interactions in crystal lattice.

Synthesis of ligand 2,4-bis[2-(pyridine-2-ylmethylidene)hydrazinyl]pyrimidine (L) and complexes 1 and 2 :

The ligand (L) and crystalline complexes **1** and **2** are prepared by using the literature method¹⁷.

Supramolecular interactions in complex [Zn₃(L)₂Cl₆] (1) :

There are two regions in this complex which are active in supramolecular interactions. *Region 1* is intramolecular hydrogen bonding between Cl2 and azomethine hydrogen (H6A) within the same molecule (Fig. 1a) and *Region 2* is axial chlorine...chlorine interaction between two crystallographically independent molecules (Fig. 2). The hydrogen bonding interaction is shown in Fig. 1 and the corresponding bonding parameters are summarized in Table 1. In recent years, Desiraju and his group has convincingly argued that the halogen-halogen interaction is a weak attractive force that can be employed to manipulate and organize supramolecular structure within a crystal¹⁸. Price⁸ and Murray¹⁹ have demonstrated that the nonspherical atomic charge distribution on the halogens is important in directing halogen-halogen interactions²⁰. In this complex we have shown two type of interactions, (1)

Fig. 1. (a) Hydrogen bonding interaction in complex **1**. (b) Hydrogen bonding interactions in complex **2**.

Table 1. Details of hydrogen bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for complex **1** and **2**

D-H...A	d(D-H) (Å)	d(H...A) (Å)	d(D...A) (Å)	∠(DHA) (°)
Complex 1				
N(6)-H6A...Cl2	0.860	2.42	3.255(14)	162
Complex 2				
N(3)-H(3A)...O(5)	0.94(7)	1.96(6)	2.848(6)	156(6)
O(2)-H(20)...O(8)	0.83	2.19	3.00(10)	163
O(1)-H(18)...O(4)	0.73(4)	2.22(4)	2.824(11)	141(4)
O(2)-H(19)...O(7)	0.86	2.09	2.934(10)	165

the Cl(1)...Cl(3) interactions (distance is 3.222 Å) and (2) the Cl(2)...H(6A) interaction (distance is 2.42 Å). Three Zn-Cl distances are Zn1-Cl1 (2.267 Å), Zn1-Cl2 (2.206 Å) and Zn1-Cl3 (2.341 Å). So our expectation is that the Cl2 in shortest Zn-Cl bond should interact better with Cl3 which is the largest Zn-Cl bond. But as the chlorine atom (Cl2) is engaged in intramolecular hydrogen bonding it remains silent in interaction with Cl3. This may be ascribed to the fact that Cl...Cl interaction is weaker than hydrogen bond. Apart from this the steric congestion may play an important role which would have been arising if the Cl2 would participate in the expected Cl...Cl interaction. Here two axial chlorine atoms (Cl1 and Cl3) interacts non-linearly (Cl1-Cl3-Zn1 = 135.40° and Zn1-Cl1-Cl3 = 121.79°)²¹ in such a way that two Zn1 atoms from two adjacent complex unit span in trans orientation with respect to the Cl...Cl interaction. The Cl...Cl and H...Cl interactions are proved by Hirshfeld surface analysis (Fig. 3). The corresponding fingerprint plots can quantitatively predict the weak intermolecular interaction in the crystal structure. The grey shadow is an outline of the complete fingerprint plots (Fig. 4) represents the 100% interaction where the blue shadow interprets the chlorine...chlorine interaction and the same in Fig. 4 demonstrate the H...Cl interaction. The donor-acceptor chlorine...chlorine interaction extrapolates the structure to grow into an infinite chain (Fig. 2).

Supramolecular interactions in complex [Cd(L)(H₂O)₂](ClO₄)₂ (2) :

In complex **2** two different types of intermolecular hydrogen bonding promote the structure to extend the structure in 3D space. This hydrogen bonding parameters are summarized in Table 1 and the interactions are shown in

Fig. 2. Chlorine-chlorine interactions in complex 1.

Fig. 1b. Hydrogen atoms (H19 and H20) which are attached with O2 atom (axially coordinated water molecule) are engaged in hydrogen bonding with the oxygen atoms (O7 and O8 respectively) of the non-coordinated perchlorate ion (oxygen atoms are associated with two different Cl2 centers). Further extension of this H-bonding (O8 and O7 atoms are associated with those centers respectively) stacks atop another complex unit. It is noteworthy that the other axial water molecule unlike the former one provides only one hydrogen donor (H18) towards the H-bond formation with the oxygen atom (O4) of another perchlorate ion. In addition the azomethine NH (H3A) also actively participate in the same with the oxygen atom (O5) of the nearest perchlorate.

Decoding of intermolecular interactions in complex 1 and 2 : Hirshfeld surface and fingerprint plot :

Crystal engineering, a very active field of chemical crystallography which tries to understand, describe and explore the multitude of intermolecular interaction that governs the assembly of molecules into crystals². A particularly striking method to locate those short intermolecular contacts in the crystal that are believed to be important for crystal assembly was developed by Spackman and co-workers¹⁰. They introduced a novel approach to

explore the crystal lattice with Hirshfeld surface analysis. They also developed the corresponding fingerprint plots produced with the help of Crystal Explorer computer program¹⁵ using the structural information obtained from X-ray diffraction studies. Particular attention is given to 3D shape, curvature surfaces, shape index curve and breakdown plots which provide a concise summary of the intermolecular interactions occurring in the crystal by mapping the fraction of points on the corresponding Hirshfeld surface as a function of the closest distances from the point to nucleus (d_i) and exterior (d_e) to the surface¹⁴. The range of d_e and d_i across the Hirshfeld surface varies considerably depending on the atoms in the molecule (size dependence) and the particular type of intermolecular interaction experienced (interaction dependence). The atoms which make intermolecular contacts closer than the sum of their van der Waals radii will be highlighted in red on the d_{norm} surface whereas the longer contacts are blue and contacts around the sum of van der Waals radii are white. The 2D-fingerprint of the Hirshfeld surface represents a truly novel method for summarising the complex information contained in a molecular crystal structure into a single, unique full colour plot, which provide a 'fingerprint' of the intermolecular interactions in the crystal.

Derived from the Hirshfeld surface, these 2D-fingerprint plots provide a visual summary of the frequency of each combination of d_e and d_i across the surface of a molecule, so they not only indicate which intermolecular interactions are present, but also indicate the relative area of the surface corresponding to each kind of interaction. For each point on the Hirshfeld surface we determine both d_e and d_i . Each point on the 2D-fingerprint plot corresponding to a unique (d_e, d_i) pair, and the colour of each point corresponds to the relative area of the surface with that (d_e, d_i) pair. Points on the plot with no contribution on the surface are left uncoloured, and points with a contribution to the surface are coloured blue for a small contribution through green to red for points with the greatest contribution. All fingerprint plots are coloured on the same relative scale and hence comparison between several fingerprints becomes easier. Because Hirshfeld surfaces nearly fill the available space, so void spaces are small, these 2D-fingerprint plots are pseudo-mirrored along the $d_e = d_i$ diagonal. Features along the diagonal occur due to like...like contacts, while the 'wings' on the fingerprint plot are due to different interaction.

The Hirshfeld surfaces for complex **1** are given in Fig. 3. The total volume of the Hirshfeld surface of **1** is 1225.44 (Å)³ and the surface area for the same is 799.25 (Å)². All kinds of Hirshfeld interactions are summarized in Table 2. The fingerprint plot for **1** reveals two major intermolecular (Fig. 4) contacts. The first contact gives the wings of the plot at (d_e, d_i) in the range (1.7, 1.1) to (1.9, 1.3) and these are due to C-H...Cl interactions (Fig. 5). The second conspicuous feature is the spike at lower left, along the plot diagonal, due to H...H contact (the diffuse pattern of blue points between the wings) (Fig. 6). Considering the large number of aromatic rings in this complex the amount of π ... π interaction is typically seen around (d_e, d_i) at (1.8, 1.8) which is also fairly limited^{14,16}. Here the π ... π interaction is 4.6% (Fig. 7). In **1** there exists a noticeable very narrow distribution points which is due to very rare Cl...Cl interaction (Fig. 8). The Cl...Cl distance is 3.222 Å and this interaction is 6.6%. We suspect that it is not a coincidence that the generally accepted van der Waal's radius of chlorine is near 1.75 Å, above this the pattern of the points in the fingerprint plot suggests isotropic van der Waal's contacts, while below this the pattern is extremely narrow, and actually closely re-

Fig. 3. The Hirshfeld surface for complex **1**.

Table 2. Hirshfeld interactions in complex **1** and **2**

In-Out Complex 1	Hirshfeld surface area interactions (%)	In-Out Complex 2	Hirshfeld surface area interactions (%)
N-H	2.2	O-O	2.7
N-Zn	7.0	O-H	23.7
C-C	4.6	O-C	2.0
C-Cl	1.3	O-N	2.1
C-H	7.3	O-Cd	1.9
H-N	1.7	H-O	20.3
H-C	6.1	H-H	17
H-H	44.7	H-C	4
H-Cl	9.1	H-N	2.3
H-Zn	1.2	H-Cd	1.3
Cl-C	1.2	C-O	2.7
Cl-H	14.2	C-H	5.5
Cl-Cl	6.6	C-C	3.1
Cl-Zn	2.8	C-N	0.8
		N-O	2.4
		N-H	3.2
		N-C	0.8
		N-Cd	4.2

Fig. 4. The fingerprint plot for complex **1**.

Fig. 5. The fingerprint plot highlighting the C-H...Cl interaction in complex **1**.

Fig. 8. The fingerprint plot highlighting the Cl...Cl interaction in complex **1**.

Fig. 6. The fingerprint plot highlighting the H...H interaction in complex **1**.

Fig. 7. The fingerprint plot showing the $\pi \cdots \pi$ interaction in complex **1**.

sembles the H-bond spikes and hence appearing in the graph diagonal. This characteristic Cl...Cl interaction is displayed on the same region of the shape index surface as the yellow and blue spots (Fig. 9) indicates the vast majority of contacts fall within a short range. The intermolecular interaction between the molecules involves predominantly CH...H interactions (44.7%). This $\pi \cdots \pi$ interaction is evident on the Hirshfeld surface as a large flat region across the molecule, which is most clearly visible on the curvedness surfaces as green spots^{9,14} (Fig. 10). Decoding of intermolecular interactions using Hirshfeld surface analysis, showed the presence of $\pi \cdots \pi$, C-H... π , Cl...H and Cl...Cl interactions in the crystal lattice, which are responsible to increase the dimensionality of the structure.

The total volume of the Hirshfeld surface for complex **2** is 578.05 (\AA^3) and surface area for the same is 526.99 (\AA^2). The Hirshfeld surface of **2** has been shown in Fig. 11. All kinds of Hirshfeld interactions are summarized in

Fig. 9. Shape index surface showing the Cl...Cl interaction in complex **1**.

Fig. 10. Curvedness surface showing the $\pi\cdots\pi$ interaction in complex 1.

Fig. 11. The Hirshfeld surface for complex 2.

Table 2. The fingerprint plot for complex 2 also reveals two distinct intermolecular contacts (Fig. 12). Two symmetrical spikes around the plot diagonal at (d_e, d_i) in the range (1.1, 0.77) to (1.3, 0.98) and (0.78, 1.16) to (1.00, 1.45) is due to H(inside) \cdots O(outside) and H(outside) \cdots O(inside) interactions (Fig. 13) respectively. The second spike at lower left along the plot diagonal is due to the short H \cdots H contacts (Fig. 14). The H \cdots O interaction is 22% and H \cdots H interaction is 18.3%. The inter-

Fig. 12. The fingerprint plot for complex 2.

Fig. 13. The fingerprint plot showing the H \cdots O interaction in complex 2.

Fig. 14. The fingerprint plot showing the H \cdots H interaction in complex 2.

Fig. 15. Hirshfeld d_{norm} surface showing the H \cdots H interaction in complex 2.

action of H \cdots H is displayed as blue and red spots on d_{norm} surface (Fig. 15). The fingerprint plot for $\pi\cdots\pi$ interaction (3.4%) has been shown in Fig. 16. This $\pi\cdots\pi$

Fig. 16. The fingerprint plot showing the $\pi \cdots \pi$ interaction in complex 2.

interaction is observed on the Hirshfeld surface as a large flat region across the molecule and is better visualized on the curved surface as green spots (Fig. 17). Bar plots of complex 1 was shown in Fig. 18 and the same for complex 2 was shown in Fig. 19.

Fig. 17. Curvedness surface showing the $\pi \cdots \pi$ interaction in complex 2.

Fig. 18. Bar plot of complex 1.

Fig. 19. Bar plot of complex 2.

Conclusion

The molecular conformation of complexes 1 and 2 has been established by single crystal X-ray crystallography. Beside strong interactions the weak interactions play a crucial role in assembling the molecules into an organized framework. This paper highlights the usefulness of the Hirshfeld analysis in understanding and quantifying the inherent interactions occurring in the solid crystals. For better understanding besides the decoding of Hirshfeld surface analysis corresponding fingerprint plots, shape index surface and curvedness of surfaces are also included. This paper also reports a rare Cl...Cl interaction which is the shortest Cl...Cl distance observed in metal complexes to the best of our knowledge.

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